

Formulation, development, and evaluation of anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects of a novel polyherbal mouthwash-An in vitro study

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ABSTRACT: The oral cavity is home to over 500 bacterial species. Some oral bacteria are innocuous, while others can lead to plaque, foul breath, and mouth infections. Proper dental hygiene is crucial for overall health. The current work sought to develop a polyherbal mouthwash with potential antibacterial effects. Herbal mouthwashes are superior than chemical-based mouthwashes due to their non-irritating and non-staining qualities. Herbal remedies have been shown to decrease dental plaque, prevent bacterial growth, promote fresh breath, and wash teeth for decades. They also have anti-microbial and antifungal properties against human pathogens. Herbal goods and extracts such as Neem, cinnamon, tulsi, amla, Indian borage, sweet basil, Indian mesquite, Banyan, clove, and turmeric offer substantial benefits over chemical alternatives. People can safely use natural products at home. It can effectively manage oral and periodontal disorders throughout life. The liquid herbal mouthwash can be quite effective in treating bad breath and other dental problems. The current study has important implications for the development of an affordable herbal oral therapy. Health intervention for low-income communities. For decades, medicinal plants have been utilized to heal diseases due to their antibacterial and antifungal qualities. The stability and in vitro antibacterial investigations produced positive results. It also exhibits substantial antibacterial action. There was no microbiological growth in the formulation. The medicinal properties of various herbal items and their usefulness in enhancing oral health. The physicochemical analysis demonstrates that the herbal formulation's color and odor are acceptable, with a nice fragrance and positive side effects. Numerous studies have found that these herbs work miracles. This herbal mouthwash makes it simple to clean your mouth while also preventing a number of oral health problems.

Key words: Oral disease, Natural plants, Poly herbal mouth wash, Antimicrobial activity.

1. INTRODUCTION:

In the late 1800s, mouthwash was commercially made for the first time. Mouth rinse was first mentioned in Ayurveda and Chinese medicine circa 2700 BC. Egyptians employed several products to refresh their breath and oral cavities, such as chewing sodium bicarbonate or rinsing with honey and water infused with goose fat, frankincense, cumin, and ochre.

The Romans invented toothpaste and mouthwash, but they used a secret ingredient: human urine. Until the 18th century, urine was used as an active ingredient in toothpaste and mouthwash due to its cleansing properties. Chemotherapy patients can effectively maintain their oral hygiene at home by using mouthwash. It is believed that the first creative depictions emphasizing the value of cleanliness and beauty were created by the ancient Egyptians. It was believed that an unclean body was impure. Dioscorides Pedanius, A Greek surgeon and physician whose works functioned as a medical textbook recommended a mouthwash concoction of the following ingredients to alleviate foul breath.

Mouthwash is an aqueous solution that is commonly used as a deodorant, to refresh, to eliminate pathogens from the mouth cavity, and to reduce plaque.¹ Based on age-standardized data, severe periodontitis is the sixth most frequent disease worldwide, with an age-standardized prevalence of 11.2%, per the Global Burden of Disease] (2010) survey.² According to the GBD (2017) report, periodontal diseases, particularly gingivitis and periodontitis, afflict an estimated 796

million people globally. Herbal mouthwashes are those that contain natural plant extracts. Herbal mouthwashes contain natural extracts from plant leaves, fruits, seeds, and tree oils.

The Egyptians employed a variety of products to refresh their breath and oral cavity. They chewed sodium bicarbonate or rinsed their mouths with a mixture of honey, water, and ingredients such as ocher, frankincense, and cumin. Chewable tablet recipes still exist that call for finely crushed dried plant material (myrrh, mastic, cypress grass, and lily) that is combined with honey, heated, and dried into balls. Actually, the invention of toothpaste and mouthwash dates back to the Romans.

Most mouthwashes are antiseptic solutions that reduce the microbial burden in the mouth. However, some may also include analgesic, anti-inflammatory, or anti-fungal properties. Mouthwash is a therapeutic liquid swished by the perioral muscle to treat oral infections. The most common method for reducing plaque is with an aqueous solution. Herbal medicine takes a proactive approach. The key advantage of taking these natural herbs is that no adverse effects have been reported to date.²

Many herbal mouthwashes contain antibacterial herbs including neem, yavanisatva, nagavali, gandhapurataila, pilu, bibhitaka, ocimum, Echinacea, chameli leaves, and so on. Some of the plants used in mouthwashes include clove, which is traditionally used for oral health because of its antiseptic, antibacterial, and antiviral properties, and peppermint, which has a cooling impact on the mouth. Natural herbs such as Triphala, Tulsi, Neem, Clove oil, Pudina, and many others, used alone or in combination, have been scientifically proven to be a safe and effective medicine against oral health problems such as bleeding gums, mouth ulcers, and preventing tooth decay without adverse effects.³

Herbal mouthwashes are in high demand since they kill oral infections, reduce pain quickly, and have fewer adverse effects. The herbal mouth wash is made from natural plant extracts. Natural extracts included in herbal mouth washes are derived from a variety of plant leaves, fruits, seeds, and tree oils, among others.⁴ Many herbal mouthwashes contain herbs including Bibhitaka, Neem, Yavanisatva, Nagavalli, Gandha purataila, Pilu, Ocimum, Echinacea, and Chameli leaves that have antimicrobial properties.

Compared to chemical mouthwashes, natural mouthwashes might have a number of advantages. The population's overall dental health may improve if mouthwashes of this type are developed that are simple to make at home with natural ingredients and can be used safely. Herbal

mouthwash not only prevents dental diseases but also relieves discomfort quickly and with little side effects.⁵

The two most prevalent oral illnesses are gingivitis and periodontitis. Based on age-standardized data, severe periodontitis is the sixth most frequent disease worldwide, with an age-standardized prevalence of 11.2%, per the Global Burden of Disease [2010] survey. According to the GBD (2017) report, periodontal diseases, particularly gingivitis and periodontitis, afflict an estimated 796 million people globally. Mouthwashes consist of concentrated aqueous antibacterial solutions that fight oral germs to prevent oral infections, cleanse the mouth, eliminate bad breath, and have antiseptic properties.

Periodontal disorders are diseases that affect the periodontium, which is the supportive apparatus that surrounds a tooth and comprises gingival tissue, alveolar bone, cementum, and the periodontal ligament. Gingivitis is the mildest form of periodontal disease, affecting up to 90% of the population⁶.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. COLLECTION OF PLANTS:

Leaves of neem, tulsi, banyan leaf, mesquite, Indian borage, lemon grass and Sweet basil ; Bark of cinnamon; Fruit of Amla, Soapnut ;Flower bud of clove was purchased.

2.2. EXTRACTION PROCESS:

Shade drying was carried out for nearly a month to prevent chemical deterioration caused by sunshine. The dried material was ground with a grinder to produce coarse powder. The extraction was done using a microwave. The crude powder was obtained after the extraction and the excess solvent present was evaporated.

2.3. PREPARATION OF HERBAL EXTRACT:

The required amount of powdered clove, cinnamon, turmeric, neem, tulsi, amla, banyan leaf, mesquite, Indian borage, and sweet basil is weighed and dissolved in a beaker of distilled water. Heat the mixture in a water bath for approximately 30 minutes and cool the solution.

The mixture was then filtered through a muslin cloth again filtered with Whatmann filter paper grade no 1. The extract was then stored in an amber colored glass container for future use.

2.4. PREPARATION OF FOAMING AGENT EXTRACT:

Weigh 5gm of soap nut powder and dissolve in 50ml distilled water. Heat the mixture on water bath until it gets completely dissolved and cool the solution. The mixture was then

filtered through a muslin cloth again filtered with Whatmann filter paper grade no 1. Then the extract was stored in an amber-colored bottle.

2.5. PREPARATION OF MOUTHWASH:

Mix 20ml of herbal extract with 10ml of soap nut extract until completely combined. Add 1-2 drops of lemon grass oil and make up the volume upto 100ml with distilled water. The mouthwash is then stored in a glass container⁷.

3. EVALUATION PARAMETER:

3.1. PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Physical parameters like colour, odour, taste and appearance were examined by visual examination.

3.2. pH:

Using a digital pH meter, the pH of the produced herbal mouthwash was determined. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution about 1 ml of herbal mouthwash was weighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and its pH was measured⁸.

3.3. VISCOSITY:

The viscosity of the mouthwash formulation was determined using an Ostwald viscometer. The viscometer is positioned vertically on a suitable stand. The viscometer was filled with mouthwash up to the mark A. The amount of time it takes for mouthwash to flow from mark A to mark B was measured.

Viscosity is measured by the below formula:

$$\frac{n1}{n2} = \frac{t1d1}{t2d2}$$

Where ,

n1 – viscosity of liquid

n2 – viscosity of water

t1 – flow time of liquid

t2 – flow time of water

d1 – density of liquid

d2 – density of water⁹.

3.4. SURFACE TENSION:

The surface tension of the mouthwash formulation was determined using a stalagmometer by drop weight method. Weigh the mass of specific gravity bottle. Wash the stalagmometer with water and fill it with herbal mouthwash and allow 10-20 drops fall in specific gravity bottle. Weigh the specific gravity bottle along with 10-20 drops of herbal mouthwash. Repeat it for 3-4 times for accuracy.

Surface tension is measured by the below formula:

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{nw \times \rho l}{\rho w \times nl} \times \gamma_w$$

3.5. DENSITY:

Density of the mouthwash formulation was determined by using specific gravity bottle. The weight of the bottle and the weight of the cap is measured. Sample is transferred in the bottle and weighed¹⁰. Density is measured by using the below formula:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{Volume}}$$

3.6. FOAM HEIGHT:

Mix 1 ml of mouthwash with 50ml of distilled water. The mixture was transferred to a 500 mL measuring cylinder. Water was added to make up the volume upto 100ml. The mixture received 25 strokes and was set aside. The foam's height above the aqueous volume was observed¹¹.

3.7. TEST FOR MICROBIAL GROWTH:

Using the streak plate method, the mouthwash formulation was inoculated into the agar medium plates, and a control was made. After being put in the incubator, the plates are incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. After the incubation period plates were taken out and checked for microbial growth by comparing it with the control¹².

3.8. STABILITY TEST:

Before antimicrobial testing, different mouthwash formulations were tested for stability. The stability test ensures that mouthwash formulations remain useful and preserve their qualities over time, prior to antimicrobial testing. The physical stability test assessed the mouthwash's appearance, separation, and homogeneity. pH stability was measured using a calibrated meter. The mean and standard deviation of pH measurements were determined to

assess their variability and changes. Different mouthwash formulations were stored on the shelf (25°C) and in the refrigerator (12°C). Results were documented and compared during a 12-week period.

4. PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES:

4.1. INVITRO ANTI-BACTERIAL STUDIES:

Streptococcus mutans isolates were tested for antibacterial activity in vitro. The Agar well diffusion technique was used to identify the zone of inhibition and the lowest inhibitory concentration (MIC). The *S. mutans* strains were injected into premade blood agar plates. After drying the plates, use a 6 mm agar well cutter to create four wells. Each well was loaded with 20 µl, 40 µl, 60 µl, and 80 µl of produced mouthwash. Herbal mouthwash was allowed to passively diffuse into the agar culture media by leaving the plates undisturbed. The plates were then kept at 37°C for 24 hours in incubator. The zone of inhibition was measured in millimeters. A wide range of mouthwashes containing different active ingredients is available on the market. It is important to know their antimicrobial activity because they are mainly employed to control microorganisms⁹.

4.2. ANTI INFLAMMATORY STUDY

Different concentrations of sample such as 6.25µl/mL- 50µl/mL from a stock solution of the sample were used for the study. The test control consists of bovine serum albumin and 0.05 mL of distilled water. The test solution consists of 0.45 mL of bovine serum albumin and different concentrations of sample. Product control consists of 0.45 ml of distilled water and different concentrations of sample. Diclofenac sodium was used as standard solution. All the above solutions were adjusted to pH 6.3 using 1N HCl. The samples were incubated at 37⁰C for 20 minutes and the temperature was increased to 57⁰C for 3 minutes. After cooling, 2.5ml of phosphate buffer was added to the solutions. The absorbance was measured using UV-VISIBLE Spectrophotometer at 416nm (SHIMADZU, UV-1900i)⁹.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

5.1. PHYSICAL PARAMETERS:

Physical parameters like color, odor, taste and consistency were examined by physical examination.

5.2. pH:

pH of the formulation was found to be 7.3 and the oral cavity is having around 4-8, this pH range of the formulation is suitable for oral disorder.

5.3. VISCOSITY:

Viscosity of the formulation was done by using Ostwalds's Viscometer. The viscosity of our mouthwash was found to be 1.04(Standard value: 3-4 and Standard limit: 0.9-2.73mm²/s).

5.4. SURFACE TENSION

The surface tension for the poly herbal mouth wash was found to be 38.66 dynes/cm

5.5. DENSITY

The density for the polyherbal mouth wash was found to be 1.608gm/cc.

5.6. STABILITY STUDY:

The stability testing of pharmaceutical products are done for the assurance of products stability at environmental conditions. This is done in order to determine the physical and chemical stability of the prepared product and also determine the safety of the product¹³.

5.7. ANTIMICROBIAL STUDY:

The formulated mouthwash have been investigated for antimicrobial activity against E.Coli and S.Aureus, the result showed that the formulated herbal mouthwash exhibited antimicrobial activity. The formulated mouthwashes are only effective against gram positive and gram-negative organisms compared to marketed available formulation. When compared to this marketed available formulation our mouthwash was showed best result like good zone of inhibition.

Figure 1. Result of agar well diffusion antibacterial assay Organism Zone of inhibition (mm)

5.8 Anti-inflammatory study

In this 10ml the formulated mouthwash has been investigated for anti-inflammatory activity by protein denaturation method, the result showed that the formulated herbal mouthwash exhibited anti-inflammatory activity. The formulated mouthwashes are only effective protein denaturation activity compared to marketed available formulation. When compared to this marketed available formulation our mouthwash was showed best result like good percentage of inhibition.

Figure 2 : Protein denaturation study for HMW

The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation can be calculated as:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = 100 - \left[\frac{(\text{optical density of test solution} - \text{optical density of product solution})}{\text{optical density of test control}} \times 100 \right]$$

IC50 value- HMW- 22.50 μ g/mL (Calculated using ED50 PLUS V1.0 Software)

Figure 3: Graphical representation of Protein denaturation of HMW. Along Y axis, Percentage of inhibition (%). Along X axis Concentration of sample (μ l/mL)

6. Conclusion

Herbs contain active components that may interact adversely with prescribed medications or other therapies. Furthermore, we may be assured and comfortable knowing that this preparation has no harmful ingredients. The use of herbs in dentistry should be based on proof of efficacy and safety. The physicochemical evaluation results indicate that the color and aroma of the current herbal formulation are acceptable, with a pleasant odor and a better after effect when used correctly. Antibacterial activity could eliminate infectious agents from the mouth. As a result, the current findings suggest that traditional polyherbal mouthwash can be used more effectively. If people can embrace and promote such cost-effective ways of maintaining the oral health. It may help treat a variety of common dental problems while having no harmful side effects. It will strengthen the immune system and aid in the recovery of oral infections. The present polyherbal mouthwash can assist people get rid of bad breath and other dental concerns. When compare to chemical based marketed available mouth wash, our formulation provides better antimicrobial activity & oral benefits.

S.NO	PLANT NAME	PLANT PART	ROLE	QUANTITY
1.	Tulsi	Leaves	Dental care, Anti-infectious	1gm
2.	Turmeric	Rhizomes	Antiseptic, Anti-inflammatory	1gm
3.	Neem	Leaves	Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory	1gm
4.	Amla	Fruit	Anti-oxidant, Anti-microbial	1gm
5.	Banyan	Fruit	Anti-inflammatory, Anti diabetic, Anti diarrhoeal.	1gm
6.	Indian Mesquite	Leaves	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant	1gm
7.	Indian borage	Leaves	Antibacterial, Neuro pharmacological	1gm
8.	Sweet basil	Leaves	Anti-inflammatory, anticancer, anticonvulsant	1gm
9.	Clove	Flower buds	Preservative	1gm
10.	Cinnamon	Bark	Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory	1gm
11.	Soapnut	Fruit	Foaming agent	5gm
12.	Lemon grass oil	Leaves	Flavouring agent, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory	1-2 drops
13.	Distilled water	-	Vehicle	q.s to make up the volume

Table 1: List of ingredients

S.NO	DESCRIPTION	NATURE
01.	Colour	Dark brown
02.	Odour	Pleasant
03.	Taste	Charming
04	Consistency	Liquid nature

Table 2: Physical parameters

S.NO	DURATION	OBSERVATION	ROOM TEMPERATURE	ON 40°C
1.	7 Days	Colour	No change	No change
2.	15 Days	Odour	No change	No change
3.	30 Days	Texture	Liquid	Liquid
4.	60 Days	pH	6.3	6.2
5.	90 Days	Viscosity	1.04	1.04

Table 3: Stability study for polyherbal mouth wash

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